

Analyzing Laptop Distribution Effects Among Engineering Students in Chhattisgarh.

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INTRODUCTION

Educators have again and again found been subject to taking after trends without completely understanding the true inspirations, expenses, and outcomes of their efforts. The quick pace of ever-changing technology exaggerates this phenomenon. Often, the emphasis on e-learning has led educators to place very much an excessive amount of emphasis on the "e" and not upon the real learning which we are attempting to foster (Garrison, D. R. (2011). As technology is adopted, it is imperative that educators have a comprehensive knowledge of both the technology being adopted, and where it fits into the pedagogical process.

The future reception and subsequent implementation of laptop devices inside the Engineering Technical education environment is undeniable. By the year 2020, mobile information movement generated by laptop devices alone will exceed the aggregate sum of information transmitted in 2015 by the entire worldwide mobile network (Harms, R., and Yamartino, M. (2010)). Acknowledging that Engineering Colleges will take action accordingly in the quick expansion of these devices, it is vital to more completely understand the elements that are leading educational technology leaders to take after, and often lead, this trend.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Technical education inside the state of India is currently thinking about the continued effects of the established amendment that places tops on property taxes (Gurwitt, R. (2011)). This has served to create disproportionate pockets of well and inadequately funded Engineering College regions. Given this, it is imperative that the available assets leveraged for educational technology be used in the most prudent manner possible. The current trend toward mobile computing and laptop devices is a noteworthy move in the recorded manners in which educational technology has been implemented and leveraged inside India Technical Engineering College educational environments. Accommodating a better understanding of the factors that have motivated this change can provide extra knowledge into the prudence of the overall movement. This study was intended to serve as an underlying attempt to identify these factors to enable other researchers the chance to expand and evaluate the overall value of laptop devices inside our Technical Engineering Colleges.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning Theories and Associated Mobile Learning Adaptations

Theory Description Mobile Learning Example Behaviorist Learning that is shaped by reinforcement between a jolt and a response (Sweller, J. (2014)) The use of penultimate and feedback applications or mobile response systems (Quizdom, Promethean, Poll Anywhere, etc) Cognitivist Information-processing theory serves as a useful model to describe the demonstration of learning as an internal process that comprises of several stages (Cronjé, J. (2006)) Collaborative online research and learning designed to enable learners to make choices with regards to the articles they read and direct a shared exploration of the articles meaning (Ashcraft, Treadwell, and Kumar, 2008) Constructive Learners engage in building items, ideas, or concepts that are personally meaningful to themselves or to others around them based upon past knowledge (Shaikh and Khoja, 2012) The use of collaborative interactive reproductions permitting the creation of simulated communities, towns, or even universes which enable students to explore the interconnected nature of their choices amid the reenactments Problem Based Learning Learners are presented with reflective problems to work to a collaborative arrangement (Ma, X., and Rada, R. (2005)) Collaborative social interaction through SMS and social media systems to work to a collaborative arrangement Context Awareness Learning is mediated by the context of the learner. This may include the encompassing environment or the computing interface being presented (White, J. A. (2014).)

Early Technologies Leveraged for Mobile Learning

Since the presentation of the personal information partner (PDA), many ground breaking educators have dreamed of universal access to affordable electronic instructional devices. Chief among the devices that offered a glimpse into the next decade of development was the Apple Newton Messagepad 2100 first introduced in 1993 and discontinued four years later (Pace, S. (2008)). This device offered the promise of inkwell technology that converted a user's penmanship into a method of text info. Unfortunately, the technology was very early in the design stage and rarely functioned as intended. However, the model of handheld mobile computing devices that easily provided for human computer interaction was a powerful concept for some educators. Taking after the Newton, different incarnations emerged, each having unique features and differing ranges of success. Examples of such include the Palm Pilot and the Compaq iPaq, which offered an early version of the Windows Mobile operating system. As these devices continued to develop and evolve, features, for example, device to computer synchronization, infrared information exchange, Wi-Fi information transfer, and cellular connectivity were added to augment the devices features.

Enter the Apple iPod Touch and iPhone

The iPhone was first made available for purchase on June 29, 2007 (Allan, W. C., Erickson, J. L., Brookhouse, P., and Johnson, J. L. (2010)) and the subsequent release of the iPod Touch amid September of 2007 (Ireland, G. V., and Woollerton, M. (2010)) offered a glimpse into the future of human device interaction. While earlier devices depended upon physical catches for interaction with the underlying software, these two devices ushered in a new era leveraging onscreen input through touching and multi-touching the virtual show screen. Unlike the Blackberry, the leading smartphone of the time that utilized a physical keyboard, these devices presented the user with an onscreen virtual keyboard and offered haptic and audible feedback

METHODOLOGY

Null Hypotheses Listing

- H01 There is no significant difference between the attributes listed as educational reasons being cited as the benefits of Laptop technologies when compared to corporation enrollment size.
- H02 There is no significant difference between the types of preferred hardware attributes listed.
- H03 There is no significant difference between the types of preferred hardware attributes listed when compared to corporation enrollment size.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Null Hypotheses Four (H01) was formulated as takes after: There is no significant difference between the attributes listed as educational reasons being cited as the benefits of Laptop technologies when compared to organization enrollment size. Because no items tested displayed factual significance, the research data supported the acceptance of H01.

Null Hypotheses Five (H02) was formulated as takes after: There is no significant difference between the types of preferred hardware attributes listed. Because three of the items tested achieved factual significance, the research data supported the rejection of H02.

Table 4.4

Scheffé post hoc criterion for significance comparing hardware preferences and college size

Reflecting on the purchasing process, to what degree do you agree with the following statement:			95% Confidence			
			Mean		Interval	
			Difference (I-J)	SE	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Public perception of the brand of laptop device influences my purchase decisions	Very Small	Small	-0.91*	0.29	-1.74	-0.07
		Medium	-0.58	0.34	-1.54	0.37
		Large	-0.41	0.34	-1.38	0.55
	Small	Very Small	0.91*	0.29	0.07	1.74
		Medium	0.32	0.36	-0.68	1.33
		Large	0.49	0.36	-0.53	1.51
	Medium	Very Small	0.58	0.34	-0.37	1.54
		Small	-0.32	0.36	-1.33	0.68
		Large	0.17	0.40	-0.95	1.29
	Large	Very Small	0.41	0.34	-0.55	1.38
		Small	-0.49	0.36	-1.51	0.53
		Medium	-0.17	0.40	-1.29	0.95

* $p < 0.05$

Null Hypotheses Six (H03) was formulated as takes after: There is no significant difference between the types of preferred hardware attributes listed when compared to organization enrollment size. Because one item tested achieved measurable significance, the research data supported the rejection of H03.

Discussions

H01. There is no significant difference between the attributes listed as educational reasons being cited as the benefits of Laptop technologies when compared to corporation enrollment size.

Contrasting the responses measuring perceived benefits with the four gatherings of Engineering College size produced no items differing in factual significance. Here, over the range of partnership sizes educational leaders appear to agree with the perceived benefits of Laptop technologies. As a result no items tested showing measurable significance, the research supported the acceptance of H01.

H02. There is no significant difference between the types of preferred hardware attributes listed.

Numerous responses to this battery of questions achieved measurable significance. Among the six items perceived to be preferences were:

- Processor speed
- Battery life between 4-8 hours
- Battery life 8 hours and over
- IOS (Apple) based items
- 32 Gb or more of internal storage
- Screen size of 10 inches or over

All things considered, the research supported the rejection of H02.

H03. There is no significant difference between the types of preferred hardware attributes listed when compared to corporation enrollment size.

Here it was determined that there was a difference of factual significance between very little and little regions giving a mean difference of $-.91$ demonstrating that little areas were more likely to report that the perception of the brand of Laptop influenced their decision when compared to very little regions. Hence, the research supported the rejection of H03.

CONCLUSIONS

Taking after a review of the results, there were differences found between the social/political pressure sources, perceived educational benefits and finally hardware and software attributes. Moreover, when combined with Engineering College enterprise size, the information revealed differences in the participant responses in every single categorical area except for the attributes listed as educational benefits of Laptop technologies. Further research ought to be conducted to better understand the sources of social/political pressures taking into consideration the

educational decision makers to likewise be cited as the sources of the perceived influence affecting the selection process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study is part of UGC Sponsored project entitled "Analyzing the Advantages and Disadvantages of Laptop Distribution among Engineering Graduate Students: With Special Reference to Chhattisgarh State." The first author is thankful to UGC committee for sponsoring the project, Principal for assistance in doing project, Members for supporting in completion of the project.

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